

RE-DESIGNING TOURISTS' SATISFACTION MODELS THROUGH REVIEW TRIANGULATIONS

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Abstract

The study attempts to redesign a conceptual model through an in-depth examination of several existing models. We attempt a thorough review and evaluation of the numerous literary contributions that pertain to tourist satisfaction. Our model takes into account the fourteen pillars that underpin the tourism business by conducting a thorough analysis of the pull strategies and influencers. A strong focus on the significance of corporations in the tourist industry works closely with the many different types of functionaries that are linked with the tourism industry. We have not only considered the aspect of quality of tourism products and services rendered to the tourists but also have given our focus on proposing strategies for raising the number of contributions from various partners and investors. One of the most important takeaways from the study will be that policymakers need to be more aware of the importance of tourism and infrastructure development.

Keywords: *Tourist Satisfaction, Pull Strategies, Influencers, Destinations, Triangulation*

1. Introduction

Tourist behaviour may reflect in various stable and pattern forms, or even related depending on the psychological need (Cohen, 1979; Pearce, 1982). The hospitality, infrastructure, service, telecommunications, safety and security, natural environment, and ambience of a location are only a few of the numerous industries involved in supporting the tourism sector (Amisshah, 2013). Overall satisfaction with the destination visited is heavily influenced by the quality of each sector's experience. These pose a problem for small and medium-sized businesses, particularly in emerging and underdeveloped countries that rely heavily on tourism. At the onset, the market is more accessible than ever to foreign investment because of globalization and liberalization, industries, investors, host countries, builders, and legislators all have a vested interest in ensuring that tourists leave satisfied. For a destination to be appealing to tourists, it has to provide both "real" and "imaginary" things (Carpio *et al.*, 2021). Constructors and policymakers need to be able to effectively plan and build a tourist destination to adhere to the sustainability principle that underpins the

expansion of the tourism industry. This must be done without jeopardizing the location's capacity to be profitable over the long term or its friendliness to the environment that it is located.

1.2 Aims and Scope

Given the importance of tourism industries as one of the promising sectors for economic sustenance, tourist satisfaction has emerged as one of the key areas need refocus through study in detail. The study intends to give a detailed review and survey of various tourist satisfaction models contributed. Despite various model in the domain exist, a detailed study of the model considering the various other functionalities are yet to be studied elaborately. The primary contention of this study is that, beyond identifying problems, no substantial research has been proven.

1.3 Objectives

- To analyze various parameters responsible for tourist satisfaction
- To construct a conceptual model for tourist satisfaction

1.4 Methodology

The current study is intended to be descriptive in nature owing to the lack of literature on the tourist satisfaction model that encompasses the role of influencers, pull strategies, innovations, and sustenance. Secondary data are gathered from a wide range of sources, including publications like journals, books, and reports, as well as websites.

2. Literature Review

Despite numerous kinds of literature on tourism accessible, only a few find it relevant to the aims and scope of the study. The following is a summary of some of the relevant literature:

2.1 Review based on the Nature of Various Tourist Satisfaction Model

Table -1: Tourist Satisfaction Model Research Focus

SL No.	Model Nature	Author (s)
1	Conceptual	<i>Aziz et al.</i> (2011), <i>Durie & Kebede</i> (2017), <i>Zeinali & Jarpour</i> (2015), <i>Dmitrovic et al.</i> (2009), <i>Majeed et al.</i> (2020), <i>Correia et al.</i> (2013), <i>Bayih & Singh</i> (2020), <i>Rajput & Gahfoor</i> (2020), <i>Manhas et al.</i> (2016), <i>Kanwel et al.</i> (2019), & <i>Moon & Yuting</i> (2022),
2	Empirical	<i>Tukuta & Oliver</i> (2020), <i>Lather et al.</i> (2012), <i>Waheed & Hassan</i> (2016), <i>Shahrivar</i> (2012), <i>Utami & Candra</i> (2021), <i>Peng & Jiang</i> (2022), <i>Yun & Pyo</i> (2016), <i>Juan et al.</i> (2017), & <i>Lee & Mills</i> (2007)
3	Both (Conceptual & Empirical)	<i>Salleh et al.</i> (2014),
4	Logical	<i>Hong et al.</i> ,(2020)

The above tabulation highlight the nature of various model constructed in the study areas. The table shows that the conceptual and empirical share a good portion of the overall model in the study area. This signifies that the tourist satisfaction model can be elaborately studied conceptually.

2.2 Review based on Objectives

Table -2: Tourist Satisfaction Research Focus by Objective

SL No.	Objectives (s)	Author (s)
1	The factor responsible for tourist satisfaction	Carpio <i>et al.</i> (2020), Roy <i>et al.</i> (2016), Jayaprakash & Mythili (2017), & Durie & Kebede (2017)
2	To highlight tourist perception, expectation, and its impact	Aziz <i>et al.</i> (2011), Waheed & Hassan (2016), Hung (2021), Ababneh (2013), Bader <i>et al.</i> (2017), & Perić <i>et al.</i> (2018)
3	To analyze the level and status of tourist satisfaction	Sabaribadmini & Saravanan (2011), Herath <i>et al.</i> (2016), Panchal (2016), Sapari <i>et al.</i> (2013), Lather <i>et al.</i> (2012), & Dmitrovic <i>et al.</i> (2009)

The above tabulation indicates some of the existing literature. It is inferred that the majority of the objectives are carried out in the analysis of the level of tourist satisfaction. Follow by tourist expectations and factors responsible.

2.3 Review based on Methodology

Table -3: Tourist Satisfaction Research Focus by Methodology

SL No.	Methodological Focus	Author (s)
1	Primary Data analysis	Aziz <i>et al.</i> (2011), Waheed & Hassan (2016), Hung (2021), Sabaribadmini & Saravanan (2011), Roy <i>et al.</i> (2016), Corte <i>et al.</i> (2015), Gnanapala (2014), Jayaprakash & Mythili (2017), Sapari <i>et al.</i> (2013), Zakaria <i>et al.</i> (2018), Lather <i>et al.</i> (2012), Durie & Kebede (2017), Sharma & Chaudary (2020), Correia <i>et al.</i> (2013), Ababneh (2013), Akroush <i>et al.</i> (2016), Perić <i>et al.</i> (2018), & Ramyar & Halim (2020)
2	Secondary Data analysis	Herath <i>et al.</i> (2016)
3	Both data analysis	Panchal (2016)
4	Survey Data collections & descriptive methods adopt.	Carpio <i>et al.</i> (2020), Bagri & Kala (2015), & Bader <i>et al.</i> (2017)

The above tabulation highlight the nature of the methodology adopted. Furthermore, the table indicated that the most widely used methodology is primary data collection and analysis for the same, followed by survey data collection and secondary data analysis.

From the above tabulations, it can be deduced, at the very least, that no research work is carried out analyzing the various other parameters that act as influencers. In addition, there has been no model discovered that equates with the pull strategies, along with innovation and sustenance of the current state of tourist products and services. This opens up a research gap that needs to be investigated further and in greater detail. The proposed model will serve to make up for the deficit in the current studies by bringing attention to the gap that was mentioned above.

3. The Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework is predicated on a pair of factors. Management and policymakers are concerned with the second set of variables, which are related to the satisfaction, expectation, return intention, and tenacity of tourists' psyches, while the first set of variables reflects the industries' dependence on other

sectors for success. As mentioned before, the growth and development of the tourism industry are dependent on several subsectors. The following is a list of the conceptual frameworks used by various industries:

Figure 1: Conceptual framework on Influence on Tourist Satisfaction

Source: Authors Compilation

The importance of infrastructure to tourism development has been emphasized by Zimik and Barman (2021). Additionally, Mandi and Co corroborate that infrastructure development has direct effects on the tourism industry (Mandi *et al.*, 2018). The expansion of the tourism sector in developing nations is largely dependent on investments in infrastructure (Mustafa, 2019). Nguyen (2021) argues that developing countries, in particular, should prioritize spending on tourism infrastructure to improve the quality of the ongoing discussion and increase the attractiveness of service facilities and vacation destinations. Tourists can be enticed to return to the destination by investing in its infrastructure. People travel to different places for a wide variety of reasons, including business, pleasure, health, tourism, exploration, and learning (Barcelona, 2019). The complexity and diversity of the tourism tourist serve as a pull strategy, encouraging tourists to try everything the sector has to offer (Nyorani, 2020; Howarth, 2022). Keeping the peace is a major issue for expanding businesses everywhere, especially in the Middle East and emerging economies (Alananzeh, 2017). The natural and cultural environment, the significance of tourism and travel, and tourist satisfaction are just a few of the factors that Shahrivar (2012) has studied to determine what prompts tourists to return.

Following the foregoing conceptual framework, a tourist satisfaction paradigm is developed and discussed at length in light of the objectives. Policymakers, builders, tourists, and the local community all need to know that tourist satisfaction is the ultimate goal for the industries to leverage economic growth and contribution. Even though the independent variable affects both the dependent variable and the dependent variable, a satisfied tourist is more likely to return to the destination and have another enjoyable experience.

4. The Paradigm

The proposed conceptual framework for tourist satisfaction was developed after a thorough evaluation of existing, widely used models in the area with careful analysis of the practical implications. Biswas *et al.* (2020) conduct an in-depth analysis of one of the remarkable models. The model emphasizes the destination's attributes (such as food, lodging, transportation, and recreation) as a means of influencing emotional and psychological aspects of the vacation experience. The consumer psychology of tourism was quantified using the cognitive-affective model developed by Bosque & Martn (2008). This model entailed an investigation into the tourist's psyche both before and after the trip. The research conducted by Lee & Mills (2007) in managing mobile and technology plays a significant role thereby accessing potential information of the destinations, which enriches understanding of the model.

Covid-19, a novel flu strain that has recently spread, has suggested a need for new models that are more effective and eminent than the old ones, and which can therefore continue the expansion of relevant industries while also addressing the underlying economic shortcomings. Although many conceptual and empirical paradigms have been developed through various studies, the current model developed will not only overcome the deficiency of various other models in tourist satisfaction, but will also correlate the modern advancement, dynamic, and tourist psychology; consider rational and aid in establishing correlation relationships between the perceptions of policymakers, constructors, the local community, and the psychology of the tourist. The theoretical framework guides maximizing policymakers' and builders' awareness of, and response to, tourist attractions, thereby satisfying tourists' needs and increasing demand.

Figure 2: Tourist Satisfaction Model

Source: Author Compilation

Tourist Behaviour (TB)

Emre and Nur (2018) define a tourist as an individual who travels more than 100 kilometres from the usual place of residence or place of employment for recreation or business and stays there for at least one night.

This seems to be more relevant for a lone tourist, but studies often overlook the fact that tourists can also travel in mass or even leave in droves. McCabe (2005) criticizes the traditional method of defining the tourist as a lay category and argues that the tourist experience itself should be the primary focus of any definition of the tourist. The difference between tourists and regular travellers can be summarized as follows: the former tend to travel in organized groups, reserve tourists in advance, and arm themselves with knowledge; the latter is more likely to prefer independent tourists (Zaremba, 2016). Cohen (1972) was an early forerunner in studying and elucidating tourist behaviour. In addition, tourists are expected to conform to local customs and manners. Tourists act differently at different stages of the tourist planning process, decision-making process, and actual tourist itself, all of which involve them making the most of access to mobile and internet-based resources to learn about destinations. The tourist of more demanding attitude and behaviour on the part of tourists, unmindful of the host and local capability, is a clear result of the increased availability of information, the broadening of tourists' horizons, and the diversification of motivations. The following factors account for tourist's behaviour:

$$TB:Sp;Mv;If;Rt \quad (1)$$

Where Sp =Spot, Mv =Motivation, If =Influencer, and Rt =Route. There is a direct correlation between the state of mind and the actions of tourists. Tourist habits and preparations are intricately intertwined with the places they visit, with tourists often daydreaming about the local culture, fashion, and cuisine long before they set foot in the tourist. Tourists' cross-cultural behaviour is psychologically fostered by the tourist's destination. Although it may seem counterintuitive, the host must make adjustments to the venue to accommodate guests of many different cultural backgrounds. All parties involved in tourism—hosts, tourists, and other stakeholders—are being encouraged to adopt a more flexible and adaptable approach by providing more options for the daily routines in terms of consumption, stay, and activities. Tourist motivation (Mv) is another critical factor in shaping the actions while tourists. Tourists, having seceded the destinations, tend to evaluate and concentrate on the tourist provision of bare necessities. Living conditions, tourist options, opportunities for exploration, and infrastructure all play a role in shaping tourists' expectations. Tourists' behaviour changed immediately, even though the tourist never stopped to consider the implications in terms of the basic, social, safety, and actualization needs. While soft drinks are typically not part of a tourist's itinerary, serving the tourist with less ice can alter perception. Tourists visiting India, where the average person is very price conscious, tourists' tastes and preferences may shift away from the original product in favour of a cheaper alternative. The epidemic (CoV19) has had a major impact on tourist habits. Psychologically inhibiting a desire to travel to unfamiliar locations (Aida & Viswanathan, 2021). From the point of view of marketing management, influencers (If) are the brand collaboration, between the product or services (in this case, the tourism product) with other internet influencers.

At first, digitalization provided the most effective medium for reaching, engaging, and persuading tourists. A person's sense of self-worth and individuality can be bolstered by the opportunities presented by various social media. The way of life is often portrayed as a portrait of the lifestyle of the tourist from the perspective of the consumer. Decisions and perspectives toward a destination are profoundly influenced by the feedback received from influential people, whether positive or negative. Tourists usually seek online resources like tourist blogs, reports, and guides to learn more about the destinations and find activities that will provide at least as much entertainment. The purpose of influencer marketing in the tourism industry is to get people to visit a particular destination through the use of products designed to make that experience more likely (Jaya & Prianthara, 2018). Customers' level of satisfaction with the marketing strategy is affected by several factors, one of which is the mode of transportation (Rt) the tourist chooses. The back and forth from destinations

affect tourist behaviour. One of the emerging concepts that have drawn the attention of many scholars and stakeholders, providing more opportunity to concentrate on the topic at hand and develop appropriate policies, is an appreciation of travel behaviour. A route map is one of the first things a tourist will look at, and it's also a crucial part of marketing a tourist. The advent of new transportation options, such as aeroplanes, boats, and automobiles, has been a watershed moment in the development of the tourist industry. From the moment the tourist leaves until the moment the tourist reaches the destination and returns, the tourist has a desire to discover and enjoy the destination. Tracking, hiking, boating facilities, and improved tourism will undoubtedly motivate and attract tourists to a particular destination. These end up being riskier, which influences travellers' choices and ultimately how satisfied tourists are. Travellers can choose from many different tourist routes and modes, each catering to a different economic class. A tourist who has a good time on vacation is a tourist who will return with satisfaction. The aforementioned are tangible aspects of the route; interestingly, the intangible route may be more or less focused on the availability of information, services, and facilities about the destination beforehand, and tourists can contribute by sharing knowledge of the tourist through reviews and comments posted on social media and personal blogs.

From what has been said above, it is clear that, beyond the traditional approach of defining tourism industries and tourist satisfaction, tourism can be defined from the perspective of various parameters. By shedding light on tourist behaviour, builders and policymakers can better tailor efforts to the needs of the destination. The goal of any tourism business should be to ensure that tourists enjoy their stay without compromising on the principles of responsible tourism. IT has a major impact on the tourist, say Sergei and Kashevnik (2020). The findings of the study draw attention to the digital tourist, establish a bridge between the tourist and the digital world, and examine how tourists' habits have evolved. Observable correlations between tourist behaviour and the built environment can be postulated. This new avenue allows for in-depth research into the topic. From a marketing point of view, customers are more likely to take on the traits of an influencer, whether those traits are subtle or blatant. And despite the positive effects on the local economy and quality of life, the tourism industry still affects the way residents behave. These pessimists sow discord between the protection of cultural and natural assets and the unethical exploitation of those assets.

4.2 Tourist Destination (TD)

For a city or town that relies heavily on tourism revenue, TD can be an appropriate designation. Stainton argues that TD can refer to any area that is designed to draw in and please tourists, with the tourism industry being a major engine of economic growth (Stainton, 2022). According to Beirman, TD is a prime example of a destination that actively promotes itself to tourists (Beirman, 2003). The key elements of TD are the presence of at least one tourist attraction and a deliberate plan to lure, trap, and tempt tourists to return. Because of progress and globalization, Kozak & Kozak (2019) argue that competition among tourist destinations has shifted from among individual businesses. According to Mutuku, a tourist destination is a place that has been built by combining various tourism-related products and services under a single umbrella brand (Mutuku, 2013). In contrast to the foregoing traditional definitions, Grauslund & Justenlund (2015) reframe TD in terms of the ever-changing behaviour and spending habits of tourists. Sustainable tourism is a new field that stems from the recognition of the human effort to promote sustainability at a destination, and Lee has addressed this issue from the perspective of sustainable tourism's guiding principle (Lee, 2001). One of the classic definitions of TD is provided by Framke, who describes it as a geographical sight that encompasses both natural and cultural beauty and can be marketed as a tourism product (Framke, 2010). Numerous studies have emphasized the importance of factors like traveller motivation, budget, perceived value, and personal interests when deciding on a vacation spot (Guo and Sun, 2016; Saito and Strehlau, 2018;

Dbbski and Nasierowski, 2017), among others. The disappearance of once-popular tourist attractions like the Coral Reef, wildlife, safaris, and other natural sights is another significant facet of TD. This phenomenon is attributable to human activities such as climate change, pollution, resource depletion, and inadequate communication (Prideaux & Pabel, 2018; Jones and Phillips, 2010). Figure 2 shows the important factors to consider when selecting a travel destination. Interestingly, studies were done highlighting the difficulties at the destination. According to Roy, the imbalance between the tourism industry and the natural environment is to blame for the negative effects of pollution (Roy, 2020). Fan *et al.* (2021) and Dong *et al.* (2019) conducted a study on the effect of air pollution on the global tourism industry, and the findings corroborate Roy's statement. The researchers analyzed secondary sources to gain a basic understanding of the problem, and they concluded that air pollution greatly decreases tourist arrival and revisit in China. Competition between tourist destinations is necessary, say Gooroochurn and Sugiyarto (2005). The study took into account eight factors—price, openness, technology, infrastructure, human tourism, social development, environmental impact, and human resource availability—that serve as indicators of competition. The second figure takes this into account. Despite numerous definitions and detailed descriptions being provided above, TD can be defined as a site that can accommodate and satisfy tourists in both the tangible and intangible aspects, under the destination branding for economic leverage and with proper guidance according to the principle of sustainability and environment concern. The primary goal of the destination is to draw tourists and sustain the local economy. According to the theory of motivation, it is critical to provide a positive tourist experience. The principles of sustainability, optimal resource utilization, waste management, and cultural preservation are essential for creating a harmonious relationship between human needs and the natural world. Figure 2 provides a comprehensive list of subcategories under which tourist destinations can be analyzed. Parameters are developed with the help of a report from the World Economic Forum's Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (Forum, 2019). The probable parameters existing at the destination encompassing the whole variables responsible as per the concept of Maslow's motivation pyramids are taken into account.

4.2.1 Prioritization of Travel and Tourism (PTT)

The tourism industry is inextricably linked to the management of travel and transportation. Travellers are more likely to visit a location if they have a variety of transportation options available to them. The scale and expansion trend of the PTT need to be studied in depth. One in four people around the world work in the travel and tourism industry, which also contributes 10% to global GDP and generates the US \$1.8 trillion in visitor spending in 2019 (Council, 2020). When tourists view travel and tourism as having personal significance, they are more likely to visit both new and familiar locations. Some of the factors that cause stress for tourists after trips have been argued by Steyn *et al.* (2004); these include a packed itinerary, limited free time, and long hours behind the wheel. According to multiple sources (Akda & ter, 2011; Bastian *et al.*, 2015; Asadi & Daryaei, 2011; Lee *et al.*, 2021; Balan *et al.*, 2009), the success of a destination's tourism industry is contingent on several factors. Hassan and colleagues have evaluated the importance of different tourism destinations in the province of Razavi Khorasan. The evaluation provides valuable insight into the potential tourism integration, uniqueness, and prioritization of the selected destination (Hassan *et al.* 2012). Quality Management Practices have been studied by Manhas and Dogra regarding the potential to improve service, facilitate the development of high-quality offerings, and contribute to the promotion of a destination's reputation (Manhas & Dogra, 2013). PTT aims to develop and overcome various obstacles, creating a branded and competitive advantage for the destination (Bahadori *et al.*, 2017). PTT wants to better utilize and allocate its limited resources. By using the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) method, Do and Chen examine the most important factors, and they conclude that the approach is useful for stakeholders looking to boost tourism performance (Do & Chen, 2013). Garci and co. used a multinomial model to investigate the mental

distinctions between tourists who emphasized the destination and those whose main concern is the mode of transportation (Garci *et al.*, 2015). Most tourists place a premium on seeing the sights and experiencing new cultures. Many researchers have brought attention to the problems with stereotyping because of the shifting tastes and preferences of tourists and the industry's focus on accommodating all tourists, regardless of background. Stakeholders, governments, affiliated organizations, builders, and communities all have important roles to play. Because of growing environmental and sustainability concerns, the tourism and travel sectors are increasingly looking to other developed nations for inspiration and guidance in shaping sustainable practices. Due to the effects of globalization and economic liberalization, businesses now prioritize FDI and other forms of foreign investment, as well as any opportunities for collaboration that may arise. It would be smart if the government and private companies worked together to ensure that businesses ran efficiently. Government policy has shifted to emphasize restoration and upkeep of tourist attractions, or relocation of monuments when feasible. The policymakers' and builders' awareness of the importance of work is another focal point that must be sustained and enhanced.

4.2.2 Natural and Cultural Environment (NCE)

The natural environment has become the "object of desire" for many Western tourists, who represent the "root cause" of tourism, which some argue began with cultural tourism (Lew *et al.*, 2004). Ecotourism is one of the most significant developments in the field of environmental protection. NCE has recently emerged as a major draw for vacationers. Eco-tourism not only helps stabilize economies by creating new jobs but also aids in the preservation and sustainable use of natural resources. Ecotourism's market value is expected to grow from its 2019 total of \$181.1 billion to \$333.8 billion by 2027. (Vig & Deshmukh, 2021). Due to climate change, ecotourism must adapt and prioritize the conservation of the natural resources it relies on to thrive (Ooi *et al.*, 2018). However, the tourism industry has put a strain on the environment and local resources, which could be running low. Stainton also makes an important observation about the environment of tourism, namely, that people are drawn to a place because of its pleasant weather (Stainton, 2020). Tourism in natural areas, says Rahmanita, contributes to the destination's aesthetic development (Rahmanita, 2018). Culture and the environment are major draws for tourists (Iseh *et al.*, 2021). The attractiveness and competitiveness of tourist destinations are something that both culture and tourism contribute to (OECD, 2009). UNWTO reports that cultural tourism makes up 35.8 per cent of all international arrivals and expands the definition of "cultural tourism" to include activities beyond those typically associated with the term, such as sports, languages, religious festivals, crafts, and cuisine. Increases in taste, preference, stakeholder involvement, local communities' interest, and the implementation of sustainable tourism practices all point to cultural tourism continuing to be the most lucrative sector of the tourism industry shortly (UNWTO, 2018). While many researchers have examined the tourist experience, Richards highlights the dearth of research done on cultural tourism as a whole (Richards, 2018). Richards and Munsters define cultural tourism as an immersion in the customs and way of life of a destination, as well as participation in artistic pursuits and sightseeing (Richards & Munsters, 2010). Hausmann has proposed expanding and improving cultural tourism offerings as a means of raising the industry's revenue (Hausmann, 2007). The increase in cultural tourism has added new layers of complexity to the management of historic sites (Boniface, 1995). NCE and technological progress in the modern era can exist side by side. Singapore is a popular tourist destination due to the city-innovative state and successful integration of nature and development. Given the close relationship between travel and tourism, it stands to reason that tourists are more satisfied if they can see and experience the journey's beautiful infrastructure and natural beauty. The preservation and upkeep of natural and cultural resources have been brought to the forefront by researchers and policymakers around the world as a top priority for international organizations. If there exists natural beauty (garden, park, lawn) at the destination

or on the way to the destination, tourist is more likely to be content and satisfied with the visit. To unwind and focus on inner selves, most vacationers prefer to be alone. Whether intended or not, NCE becomes a defining factor in the experience that tourists have while visiting a particular location.

4.2.3 Business Environment

Tourism needs to be more adaptable to accommodate the current trend, anticipate future growth, and account for the complexities of visitor psychology and destination comparison (Rate *et al.*, 2011). BE, in common parlance, denotes a wide range of businesses in the travel and hospitality sectors. Considering two types of tourism marketing environments—internal and external—and tourists typically explore the former, which includes things like entertainment, shopping, recreation, lodging, services, hospitality, and cuisine (Camilleri, 2018). Political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors are all examples of the external environment (Gregoric, 2014). According to Life, the tourism industry has minimal effects on the social and cultural environment despite strong ties to politics and the natural world (Ndife, 2014). Strong connections between the built environment and tourism have been emphasized by Zimik & Barman (2021). According to the conceptual framework, the relationship between the independent variable and the traveller's happiness is a dependent one. In other words, it showed how much money is made from tourism-related businesses by those businesses (Kasim, 2006). Conservation of available resources is also an essential evaluation from the point of view of environmental and subsistence sustainability. Sustaining economic growth and quality of life requires careful cultivation of both the commercial environment and the tourism sector.

4.2.4 Quality of Service (QS)

Tourists expect the local community to meet a certain standard of friendliness and professionalism, and they also expect the host government to have the services available to them well organized and managed. Six Sigma, total quality management (TQM), and training and development are all well-known methods for achieving this goal (Kapiki, 2012; Kukreti *et al.*, 2020; Mehra and Ranganathan, 2008; Pearlman & Chacko, 2012; Stanciu *et al.*, 2014). The public's attitude toward the quality of service delivery can be influenced by the application of appropriate education policies (Muskat *et al.*, 2013). The 5S (Sort, Set, Shine, Standardize, and Sustain) methodology has become the standard for improving efficiency and productivity in the workplace (Sati & Adam, 2019). Although it has been brought to light the significance and impetuous, detailed, and empirically analyzing of the service sector to tourism is far lagging (Park & Jeong, 2019). Al-Ababneh (2013) argues that tourist satisfaction is impacted by the quality of service tourists encounter, which is the main theme of the study. Revenue generation, competitive advantage, visitor satisfaction, and industry growth are just some of how QS delivered affects the tourism industry (Khan *et al.* 2017). QS also places a heavy emphasis on efficiency and cost-effectiveness in service delivery. The service sector should be pragmatic in its delivery and maintenance of ethical principles, given the importance of the tourism industry's thread to culture, uniqueness, and resources.

4.2.5 Purpose of Visit

The goal of any tourist is to find a location that will both satisfy them and fulfil the reason for the trip. Pilgrims, explorers, adventurers, patients, holidaymakers, business people, and many others all fall into the category of tourists. That is to say, the direction of travel-related industries is dictated by the goals of the tourist. The Global Wellness Economy (2020) estimates that wellness tourism will contribute \$4.4 trillion to the global economy by 2020. As can be seen from actions, tourists are not seeking a singular experience but rather seek gratification across a variety of domains. Tourists are less likely to visit a location, no matter how stunning its

scenery or how hard its marketers work to promote it if the place has subpar infrastructure. Attractions are crucial in drawing tourists to a particular location. Inbound and outbound tourism are both on the rise, signalling a potentially prosperous economic revival for the relevant sectors.

4.2.6 Human Resource and Market

Human resources and market growth are also critical components of the tourism industry. Tourists to the market are more receptive to meeting a tour guide and more professional service providers. Traveller satisfaction is proportional to a destination's service quality, friendliness, hospitality, ethical standards, and general quality of life. Human resource management is crucial for the long-term growth of the tourism industry because it helps to both attract and retain a qualified workforce (Cerovic, 2012). The best way to enhance service and hospitality is through well-thought-out HR strategies that include planning, training, and education (Thavamin & Kannan, 2016). In underdeveloped nations, leaders rarely pitch in or work in tandem with other groups (Sardar, 2021; Ganie & Dar, 2020). Industry boundaries have blurred and competition has heated up thanks to globalization (Manhasa *et al.*, 2016). The professional and effective method of tourism event management and expansion of the social platform is further intriguing features for satisfaction (Getz & Page, 2016). Tourist happiness can be improved through HR and marketing initiatives. To maximize service delivery and sales to tourists, businesses must cater according to the tourist's requirements. Human resources can help promote the location so that tourists have a more positive and secure experience.

4.2.7 Infrastructure

The expansion of tourism is inversely proportional to the state of the country's infrastructure (Munaf *et al.*, 2018). Tourists are obligated to visit places where the facilities are up to par. A lack of necessary infrastructure is a major hindrance to the expansion of the tourism industry in northeast India (Zimik & Barman, 2021). The tourism sector, as stated by Mazrekaj (2020), contributes to the betterment of the transportation network. Policymakers' and other stakeholders' input is crucial to the development of tourist-friendly infrastructure (Mustafa, 2019). Travellers' hopes and impressions are heavily dependent on the quality of the infrastructure they encounter there (Ramyar & Halim, 2020). After reading the aforementioned works, one can infer that there is a direct connection between tourism and infrastructure. Public-private partnership strategies are necessary due to the high cost of updating infrastructure. Officials should step up efforts on the investment front and establish lines of communication with international organizations to secure financial aid. When it comes to managing construction projects, the private sector typically provides invaluable assistance due to its high quality of service.

4.2.8 Hygiene and Safety

Both factors play important roles in vacationers' overall happiness, both in terms of the enjoyment of attractions and health (Soehardi, 2021). When it comes to tourist satisfaction, Bagri and Kala (2015) argue that safety ranks high. According to Yasami *et al.* (2021), cleanliness and hygiene are major factors in the level of satisfaction that tourists have at small restaurants. Community training and development centred on instilling a sense of ethical conduct and responsibility toward tourists is crucial to ensuring satisfaction (Alanazeh, 2017). Castro *et al.* (2017) say that cleanliness is acknowledged as a key factor in attracting tourists. Markovic and co. conducted an empirical study on the rapidly growing industry that is medical tourism and found that patients were more satisfied with treatment when they received a higher quality of service (Markovic *et al.*, 2014). Hygiene and safety measures are becoming increasingly common in industries. Many tourists to a destination shop, eat and stay in places where they can be assured health and safety will be prioritized. The organic state (Bhutan) policy is a great example of how government can

positively affect tourism. tourists usually look for a wide variety of safe dining options and other amenities at the destination. An important aspect of security is the availability of adequate medical facilities at the destination.

4.2.9 Openness and Price

There are fewer barriers to transportation and communication due to globalization and liberalization. Industries are more adaptable than government agencies, barring pandemics and natural disasters. The industries in the area are profoundly affected by the formation of the ASEAN Economic Community, which aims to increase cooperation and integration among its members (Kamil *et al.*, 2018). Information, tourism, and economic activity that crosses national borders are credited by Liu and Nijkamp (2018) with spurring productive change and growth in various fields. The growth of the tourist industry is linked both directly and indirectly to the improvement of goods and social transformation. Investment in the tourism industry requires transparency and openness to the investor. Both the positive and negative effects on prices and tourist opinions are examined by Campo and Yagüe (2008). According to Bramtika *et al.* (2018), the price has a significant impact on vacationers' overall satisfaction. Travellers appreciate the low prices and value of dollars (Khatibi *et al.*, 2018). Tourists' willingness to pay admission fees is directly related to the prices, as Bernard *et al.* (2020) show. Foreign tourists to Sri Lanka pay three thousand rupees in entrance fees, while locals pay only one hundred and ten. This is according to research by Hrysomallis (2019). There will be more money and more jobs available if more tourists visit. The growth of businesses is severely hampered by the widespread adoption of travel restrictions like the Inner Line Permit (ILP) and the insistence on restricting tourists to specific destinations based on previous vacations. To attract more tourists and build relationships with them, the need to use fair pricing is essential. Tourists have a right to be fully informed before they arrive, and should not be expected to improvise from tourists. Price discrimination still exists, even though other areas have seen significant improvements. All potential costs and price variations must be clearly explained to tourists.

In general, tourists investigate the parameters mentioned above at the destination, which has a substantial bearing on determining which tourists are faithful, which tourists are not loyal, and which tourists are not content. Tourist experience and anticipation of the mentioned criterion will be considered as the major considerations in decision-making by the tourist, which will be elaborated on in detail in the decision-making process that follows as a tourist makes choice.

5. Decision-Making Process (DMP)

The primary goals of the study can be summarized as follows: DMP is a systematic process of identifying the destination and its parameter, collecting information, analyzing information, making decisions, and evaluating for the same (Liu *et al.*, 2015; Becky *et al.*, 2013). It is interesting to note that Griffiths considered using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs as a Destination Management Plan (Griffiths, 2012). According to Dahiya and Batra's (2016) extensive research on tourist DMP in India's Golden Triangle, travellers are most inspired by the area's food, events, and nightlife. Prior considerations, such as reasons for the trip, research, and expectations of the destination, have a larger impact on the final decision, say Chang and colleagues (Chang *et al.*, 2014). The tourism industry has two distinct effects on tourists: pre and post-trips. Before the tourist arrives, a visitor to a destination is influenced and encouraged to learn more about the area. In the period following the trips, tourists are converted into devoted (loyal). The complex and confusing nature of the tourist mind makes it difficult to win tourist loyalty. It is observed to be very interesting, as it has been emphasized that appearance plays a crucial role in luring in more tourists. The ability to effectively

communicate with the host, both before and after the trip, is another key factor influencing tourist decision-making. When tourist compares expectations with actual experiences, tourist is more likely to form a negative opinion of a destination after the visit. Tourists in the DMP compiled both new and previously collected data to evaluate overall satisfaction with the trip. Whether travelling alone or with a large group, own unique travel experience will have a greater impact. To make a positive impression of the destination and counteract any negative influences, influencers play a crucial role in the decision-making process. There is a strong correlation between the 5As (attractions, accessibility, lodging, activities, and amenities) and visitor numbers. Policymakers must adopt the strategy and construct a landscape for luring and promotion. The 5As are a free variable in the tourism industry but have a significant effect on the sector's overall importance and growth. While it has a significant impact, it can be accounted for as a demerit in the post-trip analysis of a tourist. The most significant factor is the destination's image, which is promoted as a marketing tool. Tourists are drawn in by the aesthetic quality of the landscape and the efficiency with which the event is run. Tourists are encouraged to travel to areas that can be reached by road, waterway, and airway. Even if a place isn't on a traveller's bucket list, the presence of amenities and nightlife facilities is still a major draw. The host's role as an influencer is crucial to the success of the business. Policymakers and stakeholder awareness and pragmatism are highly required from the perspective of tourist enthusiasm for the visit and collaboration with various departments in making the industries run smoothly. Tourists are more likely to choose an inviting, sociable, and providing destination. One of the most important things for tourists is finding out as much as they can before they arrive, so it's in everyone's best interest for as much useful information as possible to be posted on the official tourism site. The tourist now uses social media and other official websites as a primary source of information.

The DMP resulted in two possible tourist satisfaction levels: satisfied and dissatisfied. Despite the host's best efforts and contributions, determining the basis for the division can be difficult. Such a division may prompt the host's policymakers and managers to address the concerns of tourists. Maslow's hierarchy of needs provides a useful framework for assessing the level of effort expended by stakeholders in light of the current state of the destination, the quality of the service provided, and the generosity of the host's offers. The management and the holder of the stage need to intervene in the pull strategy. The key pull strategy that will render the tourist for a revisit, and content as complaint are herd and the needful rectification is done is communication, special treatment in the next visit, customization of tourism product, bringing solution against the tourist complaint, and improving the service and other facilities. Typically, tourists complain due to services, products, and infrastructure currently falling short of expectations. Tourists expect destinations to conform to a variety of psychology. Further development in the comprehension of vacationers' actions is the separation of happy tourists into loyal and unsatisfied camps. The infrastructure, services, and appeal of the current destination must be preserved. This is why development and upkeep need to occur simultaneously.

This claims great appeal in the context of research for understanding the existence of the situation and re-engineered (if necessary) to make the destination match the tourists' perceptions and preferences. This makes it more difficult for businesses to work together and for marketing campaigns to attract tourists and turn the location into a tourist hotspot. The pace of globalization and technological progress has ushered in a new, more modern way of thinking about the industrial sector. The model provides a concise summary of the independent and dependent variables that influence the target outcome of tourist attractions.

6. Conclusion

The conceptual model's findings corroborate the significance of several factors. To understand the level of satisfaction felt by vacationers, the model provided a clear and distinct explanation. The study stands out among similar ones due to its detailed analysis of pull strategies and influential actors. The model's in-depth analysis of the importance of innovative ideas in keeping industries running at maximum capacity is another intriguing aspect. Different models from the tourism industry are incorporated into the study, and the results are tabulated and presented. The model incorporates all the different types of models while also highlighting the influencer role, pull strategies, sustainability, and innovation, which are not reflected in any of the reviewed models. The study does not shy away from showcasing the models, but rather displays the various parameters, and most interestingly, the equation that holds for tourist actions. It is with the fourteen pillars of tourism in mind that various parameters at the destinations are formulated. All of the resources at the destination are accounted for in the study's projection of tourist satisfaction.

From what is seen, it's clear that the tourism industry needs to work closely with other sectors to ensure its smooth operation and mutual benefit. The study will find useful to various stakeholders and constructors involved in improving the infrastructure and the tourism sector. The model can be applied to sectors apart from the tourism industries with careful thought.

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Appendix-1: Review Matrix

SI	Particular	Objectives	Methodology	Findings
1	An investigation of international & domestic tourists' satisfaction in heritage context: Implications for destination marketing by Aziz <i>et al.</i> (2011)	To examine tourists' expectations, perceptions & overall satisfaction towards heritage destination offering; To evaluate which travel attributes affect the satisfaction level in a conceptual framework that combines the EDP & Perception-only models.	Primary data collection through questionnaire & t-test analysis	Melaka should improve the quality of service in the hotels, restaurants, and tourism-related staff, as well as the quality of food.
2	Gastronomy as a factor of tourists' overall experience: a study of Jeonju, South Korea by Carpio <i>et al.</i> (2020)	To prove that there is a distinct and specific market segment related to gastronomy from the overall number of tourist arrival in Jeonju City; To investigate the different factors that affect the overall experience of tourists	Data were collected through survey questionnaires, & were treated with descriptive statistics & regressions	17.20% of the respondents indicated that the main reason for travelling was the food; Descriptive statistics revealed that local food satisfaction, destination image perceived quality, perceived value, tourist expectations, and costs and risks have a positive and significant influence on tourist overall experience
3	Influence of Customer Perceived Value on Tourist Satisfaction and Revisit Intention: A study on Guesthouses in the Maldives by Waheed & Hassan (2016)	To identify the CPV associated with Guesthouses, Examine the impact of CPV on tourist satisfaction and revisit intention; To examine the impact of tourist satisfaction on revisit intention	Hypothesis generation and evaluation through primary data	Improving functional and emotional values will cause increases in customer satisfaction, and Improving Tourist satisfaction will cause to increase in tourist retention or revisit intention.

4	The Influence of Tourists' Experience on Destination Loyalty: A Case Study of Hue City, Vietnam by Hung (2021)	To measure the impact of tourist motivation, tourist satisfaction, and destination image on tourist loyalty; To examine the moderating role of tourist experience on destination image, tourist motivation, tourist satisfaction, and tourist loyalty	Primary data collection through questionnaire & analysis with PLS-SEM	analyzed the relationship between destination image and destination loyalty; Found the positive relationship between destination image and tourist satisfaction
5	A Study on Tourist Satisfaction towards Tourism Spot with Special Reference to Ooty by Sabaribadmini & Saravanan (2011)	To study the level of satisfaction towards tourism spots with special reference to Ooty; To evaluate the problems faced by the tourist while they visiting the tourism spot Ooty; To study the reason for choosing Ooty as a tourism spot.	Primary data collection through questionnaire followed by T-test and Chi – Square analysis	Age, education qualification, occupation, and marital status of the respondents have a significant influence on the purpose of visiting Ooty; Safety and Roadways should be given priority for improvement.
6	Factors Affecting Tourist Satisfaction: A Study in Sylhet Region by Roy <i>et al.</i> (2016)	To identify the factors that affect tourist satisfaction in the Sylhet region; To find out the degree of influence of these factors on tourist satisfaction	Primary data collected and analyzed with SPSS	The important satisfaction attributes are the level of overall satisfaction, satisfaction with destination airport services, and satisfaction with local transport services.
7	Customer satisfaction in a tourist destination: The case of tourism offered in the city of Naples by Corte <i>et al.</i> (2015)	To understand the relationship between the antecedents of customer satisfaction by adopting an offer-side perspective; To identify the perception of the customer about the main components of satisfaction, considering so the demand-side perspective	Primary data collection through questionnaire	Public transportation, disabled-friendly infrastructures, the quality of the streets and road signs, and the cleanliness of the city is listed as dissatisfying factors; Accommodation, catering/restaurants/etc., the price/quality ratio, and hospitable local people are listed under satisfying factors.
8	Determinants of Customer Satisfaction Level in Tourist Hotel Industry Determinants of Customer Satisfaction Level in Tourist Hotel Industry by Herath <i>et al.</i> (2016)	To identify the determinants of customer satisfaction level in the tourist hotel industry of the North of Colombo. To critically assess the relationship of each identified factor and customer satisfaction level of the tourist hotel industry in the North of Colombo. To recommend the best strategies to be implemented by the hotel owners in the North of Colombo. To identify the determinants of customer satisfaction level in the tourist hotel industry of the North of Colombo; To critically assess the	Descriptive analysis of the secondary	Customers normally prefer hotels that have broad product lines, quality offerings at reasonable prices, and convenient locations, Hotels should understand the needs of the customer and provide courteous services efficiently.

		relationship between each identified factor and customer satisfaction level of the tourist hotel industry in the North of Colombo		
9	Marketing Strategy for Pilgrimage Tourism with Special Reference to Devasthan Services at Pandharpur by Panchal (2016)	To measure the satisfaction level regarding Shrine Boards services availed during the pilgrimage; To give observation and suggestions based on a study	Both Primary and secondary data collection and analysis	It is observed that the pilgrims are below satisfied with nonpayment services like medical facility nil, clean drinking water & provision of shelter sheds.
10	Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction Related to the Tourist Hotel Industry in Sri Lanka by Gnanapala (2014)	To find out the factors and forces that have caused satisfaction and dissatisfaction among the tourists who stayed in Sri Lankan tourist hotels.	Primary data from various responses from the tourist	Satisfaction factors are front office operations, hospitality, accommodations, recreation, auxiliary services, safety, price, and business support services.
11	Tourists' satisfaction at Trijuginarayan: An emerging spiritual and adventure tourist destination in Garhwal Himalaya India by Bagri & Kala (2015)	To investigate tourists' satisfaction in an emerging spiritual and adventure tourism destination; To investigate tourists' satisfaction in an emerging spiritual and adventure tourism destination; To identify tourists' likings and dislikings through an importance-performance approach, and To suggest meaningful services to make the study area a preferable tourist destination.	Survey technique for collecting data	diversity of its cultural and spiritual values, pleasant weather and climatic conditions, and a variety of tourism products Cultural diversity and spiritual values, good weather, and a wide range of tourism items all serve as motivators. The destination's amenities and facilities need renovation. Accommodation must be upgraded, including the addition of the standard level of room and room services.
12	Tourist Satisfaction Level on Destination Facilities in the Nilgiris by Jayaprakash & Mythili (2017)	to analyze the factors influencing tourists and level of satisfaction towards various facilities of the Nilgiris To analyze the factors influencing tourists and level of satisfaction with various facilities of the Nilgiris	Primary data collection by using a well-structured interview schedule	Natural beauty and people-friendly attract tourists throughout the year. Tourists are highly satisfied with the tourism attractions, Climate, and tourism facilities of the Nilgiris
13	Tourist Satisfaction Towards Service and Facilities in Kilim Karst Geoforest Park, Langkawi by Sapari <i>et al.</i> (2013).	To determine the socio-demographics of tourists at KKG; To measure the level of tourist satisfaction with the quality of the environment, services, and facilities provided in KKG; & To identify the attributes of environment, services,	Primary data collection through questionnaire	The quality of the environment, services, and amenities at the ecotourism destination is significant from the standpoint of tourists, and the resources at the park might be used and managed sustainably

		and facilities that need priority for improvement.		while also benefiting the residents.
14	A Study on Passenger Satisfaction towards Ferry Service Operated at Kuala Perlis by Zakaria <i>et al.</i> (2018)	To determine the current status of customer satisfaction with ferry operation at Kuala Perlis and to examine the influence of terminal facilities on customer satisfaction at Kuala Perlis Terminal	Primary data collection through questionnaire	There is a strong relationship between port facilities & customer satisfaction
15	Comparing the Levels of Expectation & Satisfaction of Indian & Foreign Adventure Tourists Visiting India by Lather <i>et al.</i> (2012)	To identify the gap between the level of expectation & level of satisfaction of an adventure tour of Indian & foreign origin; & To understand the relationship between the level of expectation and level of satisfaction of an adventure tour of Indian and foreign origin	Primary data collection through questionnaire	Both Indian and international adventure travellers have significantly greater expectations than the matching satisfaction level of adventure tourists.
16	Determinants of Tourist Satisfaction: Evidence from Tourist Destination Sites in Amhara Region, Ethiopia by Durie & Kebede (2017)	To examine the factors which significantly contribute to satisfaction; To measure the direct effect of each of the determinants on tourists' satisfaction; & scrutinize the indirect effect of the determinants on tourists' satisfaction	Primary data collection and conducting a quantitative research approach with explanatory research design	Tourist expectations have a considerable beneficial influence on satisfaction, both directly and indirectly by influencing perceived value.
17	Conceptualizing tourist satisfaction at the destination level by Dmitrovic <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Conceptualized a model of tourist satisfaction at the destination level which can serve as a background for designing a universal, parsimonious, short & easily applicable measurement instrument.	Carrying out theoretical & empirical research in the fields of tourism	Continuous customer satisfaction monitoring should be used as an input for trend analysis, which includes setting strategic objectives at the destination level, developing tactical and operational strategies, and eventually boosting a specific destination's competitiveness.
18	Examining Tourist Holiday Satisfaction Using HOLSAT Model: Evidence from Incredible India Campaign by Sharma & Chaudary (2020)	To study the holiday satisfaction of inbound tourists to India on different tour-related attributes	Primary data collection through questionnaire	The overall satisfaction was shown to be negative. This necessitates a thorough rethinking & effort on practically all of the criteria for a pleasant visitor experience and to establish a favourable tourist destination image of India.

19	From Tourist Motivations to Tourist Satisfaction by Correia <i>et al.</i> (2013)	To explore the concept of push and pull satisfaction and relates it with a The uni-dimensional measure of satisfaction.	Primary data collection through questionnaire	Tourist satisfaction stemmed from the ability to enjoy the cultural and social specificities of a place while taking into account the suitable amenities.
20	Satisfaction and revisit intentions at fast food restaurants by Rajput & Gahfoor (2020)	To investigate the association of fast food quality, restaurant service quality, and physical environment quality with revisit intention; & To investigate moderation of WOM on relationship of customer satisfaction with revisit intention	Both deductive (quantitative) & inductive (qualitative)	Revisit intention is positively associated with customer satisfaction, food quality, restaurant service quality, and physical environment quality in a fast food restaurant.
21	Service Quality and its Impact on Tourist Satisfaction by Ababneh (2013)	Assess tourists' perceptions towards quality tourism services; To measure tourist satisfaction by examining the impact of quality tourism product on overall tourist satisfaction	Empirical data collection through questionnaire	According to the study, the quality of tourism services has a beneficial influence on visitor satisfaction by improving destination facilities, destination accessibility, and destination attractions.
22	Tourism Service Quality and Destination Loyalty – the Mediating role of Destination Image from International Tourists' Perspectives by Akroush <i>et al.</i> (2016)	To examine the relationship between tourism service quality & destination loyalty	Primary data collection with questionnaire distributions	Destination image fully mediates the relationship between tourism service quality and destination loyalty.
23	THE IMPACT OF DESTINATION SERVICE QUALITY AND DESTINATION ENVIRONMENT ON TOURIST SATISFACTION: A FIELD STUDY ON JORDAN'S GOLDEN TRIANGLE FOR TOURISTS' POINT OF VIEW The Impact of Destination Service Quality & Destination Environment on Tourist Satisfaction: A Field Study on Jordan's Golden Triangle for Tourists' Point of View by Bader <i>et al.</i> (2017)	To explore the impact of destination service quality and its dimensions on tourist satisfaction in Jordan's golden Triangle (To explore the impact of destination service quality and its dimensions on tourist satisfaction; & To determine the impact of destination environment & its dimensions on tourist satisfaction To determine the impact of the destination environment and its dimensions on tourist satisfaction in Jordan's golden Triangle	Descriptive survey method	The level of destination environment from tourists' perceptions was high; The overall level of tourist satisfaction from tourists' points of view was high.

24	The impact of employee satisfaction on tourist satisfaction with the services of spa tourism by Perić <i>et al.</i> (2018)	To analyze the impact of the quality of services on tourist satisfaction in spa Tourism; & To review the literature and studies in the area of employee satisfaction & tourist satisfaction	Primary data collection with questionnaire distributions	Communication and personnel attitudes toward tourists are critical components of total service excellence.
25	Tourist Expectation and Satisfaction towards Existing Infrastructure and Facilities in Golestan National Park, Iran by Ramyar & Halim (2020)	To assess the expectation of tourists in terms of tourism infrastructures in GNP of Iran; To evaluate the level of tourists' satisfaction in GNP of Iran; & To recommend improvements based on sustainable tourism development of GNP in Iran.	Primary data collection with questionnaire distributions & analysis with SPSS	Tourism infrastructures can have a key role in tourists' satisfaction and expectation levels; Tourist stakeholders, particularly national park managers and tourism operators, should pay attention to both hard and soft ecotourism since each has its infrastructure.

List of Abbreviations

- *CPV: Customer Perceived Value
- *EDP: Expectancy Disconfirmation Paradigm
- *GNP: Golestan National Park
- *HOLSAT: Holiday Satisfaction
- *KKGPP: Kilim Karst Geoforest Park
- *PLS-SEM: partial least square-structural equation modelling
- *SPSS: Statistical Package for Social Sciences
- *WOM: Word of Mouth

Appendix II: Review of Tourist Satisfaction Models & Types

SI	Particular	Model Types
1	An Investigation of International and Domestic Tourists' Satisfaction in Heritage Context: Implications for Destination Marketing by Aziz <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Conceptual
2	Development of a Destination Image Recovery Model for Enhancing the Performance of the Tourism Sector in the Developing World by Phillip, Tukuta & Oliver (2020)	Empirical
3	Comparing the Levels of Expectation and Satisfaction of Indian and Foreign Adventure Tourists Visiting India by Lather <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Empirical
4	Determinants of Tourist Satisfaction: Evidence from Tourist Destination Sites in Amhara Region, Ethiopia by Durie & Kebede (2017)	Conceptual
5	Influence of Customer Perceived Value on Tourist Satisfaction and Revisit Intention: A study on Guesthouses in the Maldives by Waheed & Hassan (2016)	Empirical
6	Determinants for Tourist Satisfaction with Ghorogh Coastal Park: toward an Empirical Model by using the DTP Approach & Results of Path Analysis by Zeinali & Jarpour (2015)	Conceptual
7	Factors that influence tourist satisfaction by Shahrivar (2012)	Empirical
8	A Study of Tourists' Satisfaction in The Context of Textile-Based Tourism Destination by Suhud, Utami & Candra (2021)	Empirical

9	Analysis of Tourist Satisfaction Index Based on Structural Equation Model by Peng & Jiang (2022)	Empirical
10	An Examination of an Integrated Tourist Satisfaction Model: Expectations and Desires Congruency by Yun & Pyo (2016)	Empirical
11	Conceptualizing tourist satisfaction at the destination level by Dmitrovic <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Conceptual
12	Online Tourism Information and Tourist Behaviour: A Structural Equation Modelling Analysis Based on a Self-Administered Survey by Majeed <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Conceptual
13	From tourist motivations to tourist satisfaction by Correia <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Conceptual
14	The Impact of COVID-19 on Tourist Satisfaction with B&B in Zhejiang, China: An Importance–Performance Analysis by Hong <i>et al.</i> ,(2020)	Logical
15	Tourist Satisfaction and Loyalty of the Kapas Island Marine Park: A Structural Equation Model Analysis by Salleh <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Conceptual & Empirical
16	Tourism Marketing: Measuring Tourist Satisfaction by Juan <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Empirical
17	Modelling domestic tourism: motivations, satisfaction and tourist behavioural intentions by Bayih & Singh (2020)	Conceptual
18	Satisfaction and revisit intentions at fast food restaurants by Rajput & Gahfoor (2020)	Conceptual
19	Role of tourist destination development in building its brand image: A conceptual model by Manhas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Conceptual
20	The Influence of Destination Image on Tourist Loyalty & Intention to Visit: Testing a Multiple Mediation Approach by Kanwel <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Conceptual
21	Uses and Gratifications Motivations and Effects on Attitude and e-Tourist Satisfaction: A Multilevel Approach by Moon & Yuting (2022)	Conceptual
22	Exploring Tourist Satisfaction with Mobile Technology by Lee & Mills (2007)	Empirical